

Standardized Bayesian Accuracy for Remaining-useful-life on Censored Data

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Abstract

Accurate methods for predicting component failures and reliability degradation are critical to the sustainment of weapon systems and national security. Bayesian reliability models developed leveraging censored and uncensored data. However, there is no standard arising from the literature for determining accuracy of such Bayesian models. In this work, we offer a solution. Determining the efficacy of these reliability models relies on the accuracy of the produced time-to-failure distributions. To derive the posterior predictive distributions, samples are obtained by simulating data following the observed data's format, including both uncensored and censored observations. Using calculated posterior parameter draws obtained through Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) simulations, sample data is generated within the same timeline, resulting in a posterior predictive distribution comparable to the observed data, providing a precise method to obtain accuracy in Bayesian statistical models. We discuss how Northrop Grumman Corporation is utilizing this measurement of accuracy on weapon systems to inform future sustainment needs and current readiness.

1. Introduction

Accurate prediction of component failures and the assessment of reliability degradation plays a pivotal role in ensuring the longevity of weapon systems and, consequently, the preservation of national security. Predicting the lifetime of a component allows insight for when maintenance needs to be done and thus retains the reliability of the system.

There are a few common limitations with reliability data. Weapon systems incorporate components inherited from legacy systems, which are systems that have been in use for a significant period of time. Data collection of these systems often commences some time after their deployment, thus not all of the potential failure observations are known or recorded. Consequently, reliability data often involves censored data, which is defined in Section 2.1. Research has been done to incorporate censored data into Bayesian models as seen in (Trindade, 2017) and (Wu et al., 2021), but there is little research in developing accuracy metrics for censored data in a Bayesian framework. The goal of this research is to validate existing censoring techniques and develop an accuracy metric for censored data.

Legacy systems are fairly reliable but have relatively few deployments, thus resulting in little to no observed failures. In order to adequately capture censored and sparse data, it was determined that Bayesian models would be utilized since they are ideal in being able to model data with relatively few observations and can take into account censored observations (Gelman, 2020). However, a very critical part to predicting failures of weapon systems is determining the efficacy of the models created. We needed an appropriate methodology to be able to compare observed failure data to predicted failure data. Our research revealed that incorporation of censored data when modeling failures of legacy systems, specifically involving left truncation and right censoring, improved overall model fit and interpretability. Our research also determined that using a posterior predictive distribution with test statistics measuring the number of failures and average of the uncensored observations provided an adequate way to measure accuracy of Bayesian models.

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Figure 1: Example diagram of how data are generated.

2. Legacy System Data

Each component instance of the weapon system has a timeline from when it was first installed to the present day. In the case of legacy systems, failure and maintenance data was not recorded from the time of first installment. At some point on the timeline for the component instances of legacy systems, failure and maintenance data began to be collected. When analyzing failure data of the weapon systems according to Bayesian models, we are interested in the time since the last failure in order to be able to predict time till future failures. Thus, the first failure observation that is recorded for these systems does not provide any understanding or insight into the time since the last failure since it is unknown when or if a failure occurred previous to this observation.

In Figure 1 we see an example of legacy system failure data timelines for three different parts: Part A1, Part A2, and Part A3, respectively. For each part, the corresponding timeline (blue arrow) represents an existing, but unknown, timeline of the part. It depicts when the part was initially installed (green diamond), all known and unknown failures that occurred (circle with red 'X'), and illustrates how time can continue even past the current date. For each timeline, there is a known time interval. This interval starts when the data began to be collected and ends at the current date. Any failures that occur within this time interval are observed, or known, failures. Any failures that occur outside of this time interval are unknown.

Specifically looking at the timeline of Part A1 in Figure 1, we see that the part failed four different times. One failure occurred before the data collection began. This observation would theoretically be an unknown failure occurrence and would not have been recorded. Thus, the first failure observation that occurred after data collection began would be the first 'known' failure observation. In this case, we know the part was replaced and used until the next failure occurrence, at which point the part was replaced again. Lastly, we can see one failure observation after the current date. This observation represents an expected failure that can occur at some unknown point in the future.

2.1 Censored and Truncated Data

Since the timelines of legacy systems involve known and unknown periods of time, modeling the failure data with Bayesian models requires the data to be censored. Censored data are data where we know an event occurred within a specific time period but do not know

Figure 2: Example diagram of censoring from legacy data.

exactly when the event occurred. The concept of censored data is contrasted with what we refer to as ‘complete’ data, or ‘uncensored’ data, which is data that has a known exact event time.

There are a few different kinds of censoring that exist, however, we mainly focus on two: right censoring and left censoring. In terms of a study with a start and end date, data are right censored if an event for an item or subject has not occurred yet but is expected to at some future time after the end of the study. Data are left censored if an event for an item or subject already occurred at some point before the end of the study but the exact time is not observed. Additionally, left truncation is used when data points are removed. Typically, it is when the first data point is removed after the start of the study if the subject or item has already lived an unknown time or passed a certain milestone.

In Figure 2, we can see another example of a legacy system failure data timeline for a unique part. We can see when the part was initially installed, the known time interval between when the data began to be collected to the current date, and we can see five different failure observations. According to the definitions of right censoring, left censoring, and left truncation, Figure 2 illustrates how the failure data of the part is handled. The first observation within the known time interval is left truncated since the part has lived an unknown amount of time. Left truncation is more fitting for this observation than right censoring since it is unknown whether or not a failure observation occurred before the data began to be recorded. Thus, the first failure observed after the data began to be collected is truncated. The next two failure observations are recorded as uncensored since the times since failure for both are known. Lastly, a failure event is recorded on the current date and the observation is recorded as right censored since it is unknown when the failure will occur, but it is expected to occur at some future time. The time since failure for this observation is the time between the last known failure observation and the current date.

3. Bayesian Model Setup

Since the data for the weapon system are often sparse and censored, we utilize a Bayesian model with a two-parameter Weibull likelihood which is shown in Equation 1.

$$\begin{aligned}
 X_i | \gamma, \beta &\stackrel{iid}{\sim} \text{Weibull}(\gamma, \beta) \\
 \gamma &\sim \text{Exponential}(\theta = 1), \\
 \beta &\sim \text{Normal}(\mu = 10, \sigma = 10)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

X_i represents the time to failure, and γ and β are the shape and scale of the Weibull distribution, respectively. Weibull distributions are commonly used in reliability because of their flexibility in failure rates, which is why it is used for each component in the weapon system. The Weibull pdf is given in Equation 2.

$$f(x) = \frac{\gamma}{\beta} x^{\gamma-1} e^{-x^\gamma/\beta} \quad (2)$$

The scale parameter β is commonly referred to as the characteristic life, which means the time when 63.2% of the components under analysis will fail. The shape parameter γ determines the failure rate, where $\gamma = 1$ indicates a constant failure rate, and is equivalent to an exponential distribution, $\gamma < 1$ indicates infant mortality, which means the probability of failure is highest earlier in the life of the component, and $\gamma > 1$ indicates wear-out failures, resulting in a greater probability of failure later on in the life of the component. The flexibility of the shape parameter allows us to model many different components with different failure profiles.

3.1 Likelihood Calculation

Typically, the likelihood in a Bayesian model is calculated using the pdf for each time-to-failure observation. As discussed in Section 2.1, we have situations where data are censored, thus we have to adjust the likelihood calculation to take into account right censoring and left truncation. The likelihood calculation taking into account censoring is shown in Equation 3.

$$f(\mathbf{x}|\gamma, \beta) = \prod_{i=1}^n f(y_i|\gamma, \beta) \times \prod_{j=1}^m S(z_j|\gamma, \beta) \quad (3)$$

For observations that are right censored, we use the Weibull survival function, and for left-truncated observations we remove them. Combining this with our Bayesian model results in the posterior calculation found in Equation 4.

$$f(\gamma, \beta|\mathbf{x}) = \frac{f(\mathbf{x}|\gamma, \beta)f(\gamma)f(\beta)}{f(\mathbf{x})} \propto f(\mathbf{x}|\gamma, \beta)f(\gamma)f(\beta) \quad (4)$$

3.2 Posterior Predictive Distribution

Determining the quality of the models used for the weapon system is critical in maintenance and reliability of the system. To do this, we utilize a Bayesian posterior predictive distribution. We give a short description here of the posterior predictive distribution and associated test statistics. The posterior predictive distribution is essentially the distribution of future unobserved data conditioned on the observed values and uncertainty within the posterior parameters. Equation 5 shows the posterior predictive distribution for a Weibull model with two parameters γ and β .

$$f(\mathbf{x}^{\text{rep}}|\mathbf{x}) = \int f(\mathbf{x}^{\text{rep}}|\gamma, \beta)f(\gamma, \beta|\mathbf{x})d\gamma d\beta \quad (5)$$

\mathbf{x}^{rep} is the replicated data that would be generated under the same conditions as the observed data. The integral in Equation 5 is often intractable so simulation methods are commonly used to approximate the posterior predictive distribution. An approximation to the posterior predictive distribution is given using the following simulation.

1. Save posterior parameters obtained from MCMC methods

2. For each set of posterior parameters, simulate data using the set of posterior parameters as the true parameter. Note the method for simulating data is found in Section 4.1.

The approximated posterior predictive distribution is then used to assess model quality by comparing it to the observed data. This comparison is quantified using a p-value (p). The calculation for the p-value is given in Equation 6.

$$p = \Pr(T(\mathbf{x}^{\text{rep}}, \gamma, \beta) \geq T(\mathbf{x}, \gamma, \beta) | \mathbf{x}) \quad (6)$$

$T()$ represents the test statistic of the particular simulated data set. Some examples could include the mean of the data, or the number of failures observed in the data. The choice of test statistic is specific to the overall goal of the model and the data. For example, if it is important that our model captures late term failures, we could make the test statistic the 98th percentile of the data. For our model, we utilize the mean of the uncensored data, and the number of failures within the window as our test statistics.

4. Left Truncation Simulation Study

Including the censored observations correctly in the likelihood is critical in predicting failures and maintaining the weapon system. Some observations may seem to fit as a right-censored point when instead they should be included as a left-truncated point. In Figure 2, the first failure after the start of the window is a left-truncated point but at first glance these observations could be mistaken for a right-censored point. Right-censored observations occur when a component has been deployed for a specified amount of time and the component has not failed yet. Essentially, we know that the component has a longer life than the recorded time. For the first failure, we know that the component has been deployed longer than the time between the start of the window and the failure making it seem right censored. The first failure in the window is different, however, because it is an observed failure, whereas the other right-censored points are components that have not failed by the end of the window.

4.1 Simulation Study Steps

We perform a simulation study to show the effects of censoring on the first observation. We compare treating the first failure observation as right censored, left censored, and left truncated. By performing this simulation study, we are able to determine the negative effects of including censoring incorrectly. Data are generated using the format in Figure 3.

The following steps show how data are simulated.

1. Choose true parameters for Weibull distribution γ and β
2. Choose the number of components to simulate data for (N)
3. For each component:
 - (a) Simulate a random sample, or draw, from a uniform distribution with parameters ($a=0$, b =beginning of window)
 - (b) Simulate random draws from a Weibull distribution until failure times surpass the length of the window (w), by adding the failure time after each draw

Figure 3: Diagram of data generation for simulation studies.

- (c) For the first failure after the beginning of the window, save the failure time minus the beginning of the window as a left-truncated point
- (d) For all remaining failures within the window, save the failure differences as an uncensored point
- (e) For the first failure after the end of the window, save the end of window minus the previous failure time as a right-censored point

4. Save data for all components

We follow these steps for three sets of data representing different failure profiles for large, medium, and small number of failures in the window. The following table gives the parameters used within the simulation study.

Number of Failures	γ	β	b	w	N
Large	2	5	15	110	450
Medium	2	20	50	110	450
Small	3	70	120	110	450

Using each of the three generated data sets, we compare models when fitting the first failure as a right-censored, left-censored, or left-truncated point. The modeling steps of the simulation are given as follows:

- 1. For each simulated data set and method
 - (a) Fit Bayesian model to data using the model in Equation 1 and chosen method
 - (b) Save sampled posterior parameters for γ and β
 - (c) Compute the posterior mean distribution
 - (d) Compare the mean distribution to the true underlying mean

Figure 4: High number of failure data sets. Histograms of posterior mean distributions vs. the true value.

Figure 5: Medium number of failure data sets. Histograms of posterior mean distributions vs. the true value.

4.2 Results of Simulation Study

While adjusting one observation in our models as right censored, left censored, or left truncated may not seem very impactful for the overall model, we find that the first observation treatment dramatically affects the model fit, which in turn results in highly varied predictions. Figures 4, 5, and 6 show the results of the left truncation simulation study for a high, medium, and small number of failures, respectively.

From these histograms, we see a common pattern in the fit of the model when comparing each censoring method. Treating the first observation as left censored is obviously ill-advised since we know that the true time to failure is greater than the time between the start of the window and the first failure. Despite this, we still show the effects of treating this observation incorrectly. When treating the first observation as left censored, we see that the model severely underpredicts the true time to failure as shown by the posterior mean vs. the true mean distribution. This would result in replacing a component well before it was to fail. While replacing something before failure may be ideal in certain situations, the component in this case would still have more life left, thus resulting in wasted resources. One

Figure 6: Small number of failure data sets. Histograms of posterior mean distributions vs. the true value.

component may not have a dramatic impact on a physical system but treating the first observation as left censored on every component would result in substantial wasted resources that could be used elsewhere.

Originally, we treated the first observation in the window as right censored. This simulation study shows the negative impacts on the model when using this methodology. We see from the posterior mean distribution graph that the model severely overpredicts the time to failure. This would result in components being replaced due to unanticipated early failures. Replacing a component at failure may not be an issue, but for highly critical components in a physical system, reaching failure before replacement can result in extra costs and damage to the long-term capabilities of the overall physical system. From this simulation study we can conclude that the first observation should not be treated as right censored.

The final method we utilized was treating the first observation as left truncated and deleting that observation. The posterior distribution graphs show the model fits very closely to the true mean when deleting the first failure within the window. This results in models that predict the time to failure accurately. Thus, we would have a good idea for when a component would fail along with a degree of uncertainty. Depending on the severity of a component, we can decide whether to replace the component before a designated risk of failure, or to wait for that component to fail before replacement. In either case, we can adjust maintenance based on the needs of the overall physical system. Therefore, when dealing with similar reliability data, we recommend to truncate the first failure within the window if the time a component was installed is unknown.

5. Bayesian Accuracy Metric Simulation Study

Accurate methods to measure model accuracy are critical to the sustainment of weapon systems. Analyzing and interpreting model accuracy can provide insight into a model's performance and allow for informed decisions to be made based on the predictions made by the model. Incorrectly assessing model accuracy can lead to unintended negative consequences, which, in the case of weapon systems, can be detrimental.

As previously highlighted in Section 4.1, we simulated three different data sets that each contained a different size of N : large, medium, and small, respectively. These data sets were simulated similar to the structure of legacy system data, which contains both uncensored and censored components. As discussed in Section 3.2, the test statistics that we determined to use to analyze the accuracy of legacy system models were failure count and the average of uncensored observations. To investigate these model accuracy metrics, we performed a simulation study that illustrated how these test statistics compare observed data to predicted.

5.1 Simulation Study Steps

For each simulated data set, we derived a posterior predictive distribution as our means to compare our model to the respective simulated data set. To do this, we first used MCMC methods to obtain posterior parameters. Next, for each set of posterior parameters, we followed the same method we used for simulating data; however, in place of the true parameters, we used the set of posterior parameters. This provided us with a posterior predictive distribution. We then computed the two test statistics, or posterior predictive checks, and their respective p-values and created visualizations of their comparisons to the simulated data.

Figure 7: Large number of failure data sets. Histograms of posterior mean distributions vs. the true value.

Figure 8: Medium number of failure data sets. Histograms of posterior mean distributions vs. the true value.

5.2 Results of Simulation Study

In Figures 7, 8, and 9, we can see the posterior predictive checks for the large, medium, and small simulated data sets, respectively. Each of these checks show the true test statistics compared to the model test statistics, which are illustrated in the form of a distribution.

Based on these results shown in Figures 7, 8, and 9, we determined that in the case of a data set containing a low number of failures, we would only look at the failure count test statistic since it best represents data with small counts. There are not enough data to use the average of the uncensored observations for comparison in this case. However, when the data contains a medium to large number of failures, it is appropriate to use both the failure count and the average of the uncensored observations since there are enough data in both to adequately compare the data.

To determine a good model fit, we would want to see the red vertical line, which represents the true test statistic, to lie somewhere within the most dense area of each test statis-

Figure 9: Small number of failure data sets. Histograms of posterior mean distributions vs. the true value.

tic's respective distribution. In Figures 7, 8, and 9, we can see that the posterior predictive checks indicate adequate model fits for all three data sets. Based on these results and the comparisons that can be made between the observed data and predicted data through the posterior predictive check distributions, we determined that the failure count and average of the uncensored observations test statistics provide an accurate and efficient way to interpret Bayesian model accuracy of legacy system data.

6. Conclusion

In this research paper, we addressed the critical issue of accurately predicting component failures and assessing reliability degradation in the context of weapon systems and national security. We focused on Bayesian reliability models, which are well-suited for handling censored and sparse data commonly encountered in legacy system data.

Through a comprehensive exploration of censored data, left truncation, and Bayesian model setup, we highlighted the challenges and nuances associated with modeling legacy system data. In particular, we conducted a simulation study to demonstrate the impact of treating the first observation within a data window as right censored, left censored, or left truncated. The results underscored the importance of correctly handling this initial observation, with left truncation emerging as the most accurate and sensible approach. We conducted another simulation study to determine effective methods for measuring Bayesian accuracy given legacy data. We found that using a posterior predictive distribution with test statistics measuring the number of failures and average of the uncensored observations to adequately capture model accuracy.

Moving forward, we would be interested in diving into utilizing the first observation in the model rather than deleting the observation. We are also interested in looking at further failure distributions for the simulation studies and performing cross-validation in association with the posterior predictive check.

REFERENCES

- Gelman, Andrew. Bayesian Data Analysis, Third Edition. Shi Jie Tu Shu Chu Ban Gong Si, 2020.
- Trindade, David, and Swami Nathan. "Analysis of Repairable Systems with Severe Left Censoring or Truncation." *Quality Engineering*, vol. 30, no. 2, 2017, pp. 329-338, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08982112.2017.1343481>.
- Wu, Ke, et al. "Statistical Inference of Left Truncated and Right Censored Data from Marshall Olkin Bivariate Rayleigh Distribution." *Mathematics*, vol. 9, no. 21, 2021, p. 2703, <https://doi.org/10.3390/math9212703>.